

Updated Guidance for D4.5 – Individual sectoral strategies

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V3.0 - 30th August 2024

V2.0 - 18th December 2023

V1.0 - 31st October 2023

There should be one complete and stand-alone strategy for each of the six sectors. These will be combined to make the D4.5, but the idea is that you develop a product for your sector that can be used by this sector without needing to read the whole of D4.5.

Purpose of this document:

- Shared understanding of what each sectoral strategy (D4.5) should contain.
- This will generate the deliverable D4.5 (and D4.6 – infographics).
- These are part of the ingredients for the EU and MS route maps (D4.7).
- The route maps are cross-sectoral and have a different audience but will need to draw on insights from your sectoral transformation strategies.

Purpose of the sectoral strategies:

- Documented set of actions for the sectoral community of practice (CoP) to implement between 2025 -2030 and until 2040, 2050.
- Stretch focus – beyond business as usual to transformation (or towards transformation)
- Something concrete to cement the CoP developed over the period of the project

Proposed audience:

Sectoral associations, businesses, policy makers and consultants working with the sector – in other words who has been contributing to the RTs, who is part of your CoP, who is needed to deliver the strategy at EU and MS level.

We must write a deliverable that is satisfactory as a research product.

But the main audience for the stand-alone strategies need a concise document that focusses on the need for change & strategic actions to get us to our vision of mainsteamed NbS

We propose that some sections (see Fig X p X) can be removed for the sectoral strategies to make them suitable for a non-research audience. The visualisation (infographics) & key messages can also help engage policy and practice stakeholders.

Focus of the Sectoral Strategies:

The strategies should be as concise as possible and focus on the specific transformation we have worked on in MERLIN.

The focus should be on the ‘cooperation points’ developed in D4.1 and discussed in the 2nd & 3rd Round Tables.

The focus should be on how the sector can support mainstreaming freshwater restoration and/or NbS that will deliver as many Green Deal goals as possible (with the emphasis on biodiversity and climate adaptation/mitigation goals). In general, MERLIN focusses on large-scale, rural, interventions.

Be clear about the vision (where the sector wants to be) and the mission (what is your role in reaching that vision) – what is the outcome(s) that the strategy will help to deliver.

This means the sectoral strategies should not try to cover all possible changes in the sector, particularly not those that are not directly related to mainstreaming freshwater NbS, or it will be impossible to consolidate the points into a clear and credible strategy.

Geographical Scale:

The sectoral strategies offer one way to ‘upscale’ from the regional scalability plans (driven by the case studies in WP1-2) to the Member State and EU levels by focussing on changes within a sector across the EU. If it is relevant, global initiatives or those reaching beyond the EU can be used. The scale(s) for the strategy will reflect the proposed audience (e.g. PIANC is a global organisation).

It is therefore about the ‘top down’ support from organisations and institutions to the ‘bottom up’ local restoration projects.

Temporal Scale:

We suggest that overall, the strategy aligns with the Green Deal e.g. to deliver the outcomes by 2030 where possible.

There may be important sectoral activities taking place before or after this date. The strategy can have multiple deadlines, but the aim is to get action started in the next five years.

It is also useful to have longer term vision and hopes for actions until 2040 and 2050.

Overview of workplan:

Note: The final draft strategies are due [end of October 24] to enable the feedback from teams and CoP (November) and start the infographics based on the final draft. In addition to that to enable the lead (WWF) to combine them into the formal MERLIN deliverable template and finalise all the details before winter holidays in time for final comments from the SG, coordinators and to submit by end of Jan 2025. They cannot be delivered late!

Figure 1: Workplan and Timelines

Overview of Structure

This follows the guidance and template provided before, but we have streamlined things and also offered some things as optional to help you focus on completing all the sections by end October.

Section	Rationale
Title page	Title and image for Your strategy
Inside Cover	Authors, version, acknowledgments etc
Key messages (1 pp)	Summary points of the strategy
Introduction (1-2pp)	Short overall introduction to MERLIN (use earlier deliverables)- defns NbS, transformation etc Purpose of a Strategy & what is your 'sector'
Methodology (1-2pp)	How the strategy was developed, basis for the arguments- <i>Details in the Annex, just main points</i>
Why is change needed? (1-2 pp)	<p>What problems are affecting the sector, or what problems do the sector create? What is the sector seeking, why do they want change? (Broad)</p> <p>Narrow the focus to freshwater restoration & 'MERLIN measures' and how these measures relate to the sector.</p> <p>Clear that change is needed, what change is needed, and role of the sector for the agreed cooperation points (specific areas = MERLIN unique contribution)</p>
Vision (1 pp)	What will change, why is this better?
Strategy actions (as many pages as need)	What & Why, who, when. Summary Table
Discussion (1-2 pp)	What does this mean for mainstreaming? Differences across Europe, Readiness for change?
Concl & next steps (1pp)	Summary of findings, and what will/should happen next
Annexes & references	More details (for reviewers), list of cited references (evidence base)

Figure 2: Structure of the Strategy at a glance

The green boxes signify where sections can be removed once the deliverable is submitted to make the Strategy more suited to a practical audience.

You can merge Introduction and Why change is needed if the content is covered. You can adapt the titles to fit your content – if the content is covered.

Formatting and Editing:

*Experience shows that when sharing on Google Drive or Next Cloud and when merging comments from multiple non-MERLIN partners, it is best to use a **plain word template**.

Always use the following to ensure an easy to read and easy to format final product:

- Image for the cover page
- Numbered headings
- New page for each section
- Use introduction and summary sentences for each section (when more than a page) to help reader remember the main points/purpose of the section.
- Please capitalise Strategy and Sector
- Please avoid putting things in italics – MERLIN template uses aqua bold font for emphasis
- Quotes can be in-line with plain text or inset within a paragraph. Please use “marks” and provide a source (interview or RT1/2/3 + stakeholder number or stakeholder type but not specific individual/organisation).
- Cross references between sections (only the label e.g. see also action A in section 5.1 not the full title of the heading)
- Captions for the tables and figures
- Citations for all references to existing documents (including MERLIN documents) using the APA 6th style (author, date) in the text, full list at the end: author, date, title, publication details or weblink.
 - Please use citations, see reviewer feedback from RP1 who almost rejected D4.1 for lack of strong evidence base in places
- Use hyperlinks in the text to refer to online resources but also need a citation as well (in case link breaks or changes).
- Abbreviations and Acronyms spelt out first time used and put them in a table at start of doc
- Use UK English spelling and grammar
- MERLIN Fonts:
 - Headings – Yeseva One 14
 - Key messages – Yeseva One 11
 - Normal text: Work Sans 9

By the final deliverable - the sectoral lead should put their final draft into the MERLIN deliverable template. This template will be circulated/available on Google Drive or Next Cloud and available from the middle of October.

The MERLIN template for a box is:

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The Merlin template for a table is:

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Terminology:

- Use UN definition for NbS but IUCN global standard to explain how NbS should be implemented
- The Steering Group are discussing terminology – the draft list of terms can be found [here](#) on Google Drive, please use these definitions for now.
- Please use standardised list of CS names: <https://nx19846.your-storageshare.de/f/871858>

Rigorous research:

To be well reviewed, comply with research ethics and allow publication that will have impact (academic and **non-academic**) we need proper data collection and analysis.

1. Always get informed consent when interacting with anyone outside the MERLIN consortium. This involves (1) providing information about the purpose of the research, how the data will be used, anonymity and confidentiality, GDPR etc and (2) checking that the person(s) are comfortable with this and agree we can use their information . If unsure, please ask Kirsty or Alhassan but it is the same process we've used for interviews and RT up to now.
2. Where possible, record these interactions so we can use their actual words when reviewing our evidence. If not, take good notes. Use the Zoom (or equivalent platform) to make a transcript but please check and correct them. Hutton has limited resources to transcribe files but we can't cover everything - please ask if you need help.
3. Please file these recordings and notes so we have access to them for our work. If anonymised, they can go on the Nextcloud, but if not anonymised (most of them, as it is time consuming to anonymise) then on the restricted Google Drive folder. Each sectoral team should make (or ask WWF to make) their own folder in Google Drive.
4. Please keep the secondary data sources (reports, indicators, policy documents) in a folder so that any references made to documents (or datasets) can be checked by others if required. Always cite these sources in the document so we can trace the evidence trail.
5. Be clear about how you have reviewed the data (which sources) and how you have summarised and synthesised these insights, including reflection on where there are gaps in your knowledge, potential bias, or multiple possible interpretations of the same material.

Suggestions:

WP4 is designed to be cumulative – so please reuse the information and thinking you've developed in the earlier deliverables, the RT notes, the CS files, all the meeting notes and the desktop reviews.

Plan the engagement and how you will divide up your resources – better to have a focussed document that is well supported by those who can implement it than an ambitious content and run out of time to discuss it with relevant stakeholders.

Consider if you want/need to translate the key messages and infographics into any relevant languages and who can help check the AI drafts. Please ask for their help early in the process.

Use plenty of visuals – diagrams, graphs, maps, photos.... To tell the story.

The strategies may be read by non-EU readers, so consider a footnote to explain EU policies etc.

Plain Word Template for the draft sectoral strategy

Title page:

Image and title for YOUR strategy

Inside page:

Authors list

Organisation: list of individuals:

Date:

Version number:

Cite as:

Acknowledgements:

Key Messages:

Up to 10 numbered sentences with the main messages and/or table of actions

This page is the one that will be read the most and potentially have most impact. It is the basis for your visualisation.

Table of Contents

Abbreviations and Acronyms table:

1. Introduction

1-2 pages

Explain the MERLIN project, and its overall objective including ambition to transform way we work with Nature, define the sector and the concept of a community of practice to co-create an action plan to mainstream NbS.

Here (or in section 3) define key terms: NbS, mainstream, transformation

Checklist:

- Have you explained the MERLIN project and purpose of Strategy?
- Have you defined the sector/community of practice?

2. Methodology

1-2 pages

What are the sources of information used for this strategy?

Any caveats, problems, suggestions if doing this again? [if there are minority opinions or unresolved conflicts over content, you could write them here?]

Reuse the figure in WP4 presentations at consortium meetings to show the process of building the CoP and strategies

Ensure you have responded to the comments made across all the RTs.

Put details in the Annex

Checklist:

- Is the process described?
- Is it clear where the evidence for the actions comes from?
- Have you noted where there were disagreements and problems?

3. Why is change needed?

1-2 pages

What is the relationship between the sector and MERLIN?

Narrow the focus to freshwater restoration & 'MERLIN measures' and how these measures relate to the sector.

What are the current problems?

Note here the problems with the freshwater environment (what needs restoring) but also, to follow NbS global standards, what are the societal consequences?

What problems are affecting the sector, or what problems do the sector create? What is the sector seeking, why do they want change?

Also if relevant, current actions already trying to address the issue (and where gaps remain)

What is the sector's role in resolving these problems?

In this section, you will need to ensure it is clear that change is needed, what change is needed, and why the sector has a role to play.

Here, if not in the introduction, add definitions of NbS and explain the specific types of restoration being addressed with the sector.

What is the focus of the Strategy?

From D4.1, this was quite contested with some sectors. Focus on the agreed cooperation points (see low hanging fruits presented (use summary slides from Vienna Meeting where you already summarised this)

Put details in Annex if this section is getting too long. Consider using a box to provide an example.

Checklist:

- Is it clear why change is needed?
- Is it clear how the sector is involved (affected by and/or affect freshwater environments)?
- Is it clear what the focus of the strategy is (specific focus on freshwater rural...)?

4. What is the vision/goal of the strategy?

1-2 pages

Vision and mission for this sector

By 2030, 2040, 2050 what do you want to happen?

You can have an overall goal and then sub objectives.

What will achieving this goal and objectives mean for the overall goals of MERLIN and Green Deal?

Checklist:

- Is it clear what the Strategy wants to achieve and how long it might take?

- Is it clearly linked back to the aims of MERLIN (section 1) and addresses challenges (section 3)?

5. Strategic Actions

1-2 pages per action

Identify the main actions that could be taken to get to the goal/vision - this is the core of the strategy and the most important part.

Consider the practices of the sector themselves, public policy changes (build on D4.3 and DTR plus anything specific to the sector), value chain changes (by consumer or other actors in the market – build on D4.4), finance (from WP3F and RSPs).

Showcase good practice from MERLIN Case Studies where possible, also draw on non-MERLIN examples

Suggest around 4-5 maximum.

Action A: [add name of the action here]

Paragraph describing what the action is

Why is this action needed?

Paragraph describing why the action is needed, how does it help respond to the challenges and get us towards the vision/goals?

Who could help deliver this action?

Paragraph describing what types of stakeholders should be involved, what are the roles and responsibilities (including accountability or funding)

Use the stakeholder typology in use for WP1/4 stakeholder mapping tool

When will the action be taken?

Paragraph describing when this can start and when action likely to be completed, is it a quick win or long term...

Is the action dependent on other actions in the strategy?

If possible, add a box that provides an example of the action being practiced somewhere, for inspiration. Or a particular aspect that you want to provide more detail for.

Action B, C, etc....

Summary Table of Actions

Table with column of actions and columns for who/when [use the slides presented 28/8/24]

Checklist:

- Have you described each action, explained why it is needed, who will do it and when it should start/finish?
- Do you have a summary table or list of the actions (to copy and paste into the key messages)?
- Have you got some boxes of examples from MERLIN or other cases?

6. Discussion

1-2 pages

Here you need to discuss the list of actions and reflect on what they might mean. Please add some reflections on the following:

Are there important differences between Member States or regions to consider?

Mandatory

You have been telling us that the situation varies in different contexts. Please write a paragraph illustrating some important differences and how this might affect putting the actions into practice.

Here you might also want to reflect on different governance levels, whether action is needed at the local level or action is needed by EU or national stakeholders to guide/enable local actions.

[this was originally in the action section 5 but many have not filled it in. For those who have done it in section 5, please keep it there. For the others, we moved it to make it easier for you to fill in].

Do the actions require help from other Sectors?

Mandatory

Which actions require change from other sectors? Which sectors? Are there existing levers to make these cross-sectoral activities happen? If not, why not and what is needed? Will any other sector resist the actions above and if so, why?

These can be the other 5 ‘MERLIN’ sectors and further sectors (e.g. forestry, tourism, bio-energy). Please be explicit and name these sectors.

Progress on mainstreaming

Mandatory

How ‘ready’ is the sector (or parts of the sector) to transform? Are they currently resisting change, preparing for change, navigating the change or institutionalising the change?

[Previously called ‘readiness’]

Optional further aspects of the discussion

Use the transformation matrix to discuss the actions (see table below) – put the strategic actions in the appropriate cell (s) – if there are gaps, what does this mean? Are there a mix of types of actions? [this was previously in the Vision section 4]

	Create (to fill gaps)	Maintain (build on)	Disrupt (remove barriers)
Personal	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing
Political			
Practical			

How will we know if the action has taken place – what will have changed? [this was originally in the action section 5 but many have not filled it in. For those who have done it in section 5, please keep it there. For the others, we moved it to make it easier for you].

Does the Strategy help towards a more ‘just’ transformation – what are the implications of the strategy for representation, procedures and distribution of outcomes?

Is 'transformation' likely to happen?

Checklist:

- Have you noted how things might differ across Europe?
- Have you noted where the sector also need input from other sectors?
- Have you discussed the overall set of actions and if they are likely to move from the current challenges to the vision of the strategy? How ready is the sector for change?
- Optional – have you used the transformation matrix, thought about how to monitor and evaluate change, whether the transformations will be 'just'?

Conclusion and Next Steps

0.5 page

Summarise the main content of the strategy.

Explain what is planned for the CoP (from Feb 25 to end of the project and then beyond) by the sectoral team.

Checklist:

- Is there a summary of the main findings?
- Is it clear what will happen next (in your control) and what you would like to happen in the future (beyond your control)?

Visualisation

1 page

Any relevant annexes with further material

e.g. summary of the types of stakeholder/target audience list etc

List of references

Please list all references in alphabetical order using APA 6th style (if working with a reference software) e.g.

Journal example:

Baulenas, E., & Sotirov, M. (2020). Cross-sectoral policy integration at the forest and water nexus: National level instrument choices and integration drivers in the European Union. *Forest Policy and Economics*, 118, 102247. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2020.102247>

Report example:

Baldock, D., & Bradley, H. (2023). *Transforming EU land use and the CAP: a post-2024 vision*. Retrieved from <https://ieep.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/09/Transforming-EU-land-use-and-the-CAP-a-post-2024-vision-paper-IEEP-2023.pdf>